

THE ROLE OF INDONESIA TRADE PROMOTION CENTER (ITPC) IN PROMOTING INDONESIAN COFFEE BEANS EXPORT TO THE UNITED STATES 2021–2022

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ABSTRACT

Coffee beans are one of Indonesia's leading commodities and have significant potential for expansion in international market. The United States (US) is a major export destination for Indonesian coffee beans and has long served as one of Indonesia's key trading partners. To increase coffee exports to the US, the Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Trade, has undertaken various initiatives efforts to promote coffee beans to the US market. The Indonesian Trade Promotion Center (ITPC) is an extension of the government specifically tasked with conducting promotions abroad. There are 21 official ITPC offices operating worldwide. In 2022, ITPC contributed to an increase in the export value of coffee beans to the US. The Ministry of Trade of the Republic of Indonesia, through its export promotion agency, the Indonesian Trade Promotion Center (ITPC), conducts promotional activities based on four main activities, Export Support Services, Marketing, Research and Publications. Through these four approaches, ITPC Los Angeles and ITPC Chicago have successfully promoted coffee beans to the US and attracted American buyers, resulting in increased coffee beans exports to the country. ITPC actively participates in various exhibitions to achieve national export goals. These activities include business matching, organizing trade expos, and strengthening collaboration with government institutions. As such, these initiatives are expected to continue boosting the export value of Indonesian coffee beans, particularly to the US market. ITPC maximizes its capabilities in promoting coffee beans to the US by directly connecting buyers with coffee suppliers and exporters. ITPC has demonstrated an effective role in implementing export export promotion activities.

Keywords: ITPC, Promotion, Export, Coffee Beans

INTRODUCTION

Export Promotion Agencies (EPAs) are national institutions established to facilitate the promotion of a country's export products. In Indonesia, this role is carried out by the Indonesian Trade Promotion Center (ITPC), an overseas representative office under the Ministry of Trade of Indonesia as a government agency. According to the Ministry of Trade (2024) there are around 21 ITPC offices currently operating around the world. Indonesia has established two ITPC offices in the United States, one in Los Angeles and the other in Chicago. ITPC Los Angeles office was established in 2000, while ITPC Chicago office opened in 2008 (CNBC Indonesia, 2018). These offices as trade facilitators, connecting Indonesian exporters with foreign buyers and strengthening bilateral trade relations.

Coffee is one of Indonesia's most significant export commodities and has consistently contributed to the country's non-oil and gas export performance. Indonesia exported 387.26 thousand tons of coffee in 2021, increasing to 437.56 thousand ton in 2022 an annual growth of 12.99% (BPS, 2023). The United States remained the largest importer of Indonesian coffee, surpassing India, Egypt, Germany, and Malaysia (BPS, 2023). This condition indicates strong demand and strategic opportunities for Indonesian coffee in the U.S market. Indonesia's coffee exports to the United States experienced substantial growth in 2022, reaching 55.87 thousand tons with a value of USD 268.92 million the highest in recent years. The Indonesian Trade Promotion Center (ITPC) is recognized as playing a supportive role in this increase by facilitating buyers, conducting promotional events, and strengthening market acces. According to Lederman *et al.* (2006) EPAs typically carry out four major categories export promotion activities: country image building, export support service, marketing, and market reseach and publications. These four components serve as a comprehensive analytical model for examining ITPCS's performance.

Although ITPC has played an increasingly active role in promoting Indonesian coffee, empirical studies that specifically analyze ITPC's promotional strategies in the U.S using the Lederman *et al.* (2006). EPA model particularly during the post pandemic period of 2021-2022 remain limited. Most existing studies discuss ITPC in general terms or focus on non-coffee commodities, leaving a gap in understanding sector specific strategies for a high value agricultural commodity such as coffee. To address this gap, this study aims to analyze how ITPC promoted Indonesian coffee bean export to the United States during 2021-2022 using the Export Promotion Agency (EPA) framework developed by Lederman *et al.* (2006).

This section establishes the relevance of coffee exports to Indonesia's economy, highlight the strategic position of the U.S. market, and frames the analysis using a recognized theoretical model. This discussion of previous studies is presented in the following section to ensure a clearer separation between the introduction and literature review. EPAs are government instituions established to assist exporters in accessing international markets. According to Lederman *et al.* (2006) EPAs operate through four key activities: country image building, export support services, marketing and market research and publications. These components serve as a conceptual foundation for understanding how EPAs influence export performance across different countries.

Country image building, The formation of a country's image involves efforts to strengthen its reputation abroad through advertising, promotional events, cultural diplomacy, and advocacy. Welch *et al.* (1998) emphasise that nation branding is closely related to international networks, as countries must develop global relationships to gain recognition and trust from foreign buyers. In the context of EPAs, nation branding enhances the perceived quality and competitiveness of export products. Lederman *et al.* (2006) argue that strong national brands help exporters differentiate their products in highly competitive global

markets. This is particularly relevant for coffee-producing countries, where branding often influences consumer demand and their willingness to pay for premium quality products.

Export support services refer to technical assistance, training, regulatory guidance, logistics facilitation, access to trade finance, customs procedures, and pricing strategies (Lederman *et al.*, 2006). These services are essential for reducing information asymmetries and transaction costs often faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Compared to other researchers Cruz (2014) emphasises that export support services provided by EPAs can significantly reduce barriers for new exporters, thereby boosting their confidence in entering foreign markets. Hapsari and Haqqi (2015) also highlight how ITPC Chicago previously supported Indonesia during the economic crisis by strengthening bilateral trade relations and guiding exporters.

Marketing is the primary function of EPAs, which includes trade fairs, exhibitions, business missions, business matchmaking, and follow-up consultations with buyers. According to Lederman *et al.* (2006) marketing programmes expand the visibility of exporters, enable direct interaction with buyers, and increase opportunities for trade agreements. Sunaryo (2019) supports this by explaining that Indonesian trade representatives actively carry out marketing activities that directly contribute to increased exports especially coffee commodities. Experts agree that marketing through international exhibitions provides two main benefits: (1) direct access to international buyers, and (2) the opportunity to showcase product quality through demonstrations or cupping sessions (Cruz, 2014).

Market research and publications include the provision of market surveys, online information portals, export publications, importer databases, and sectoral analyses (Lederman *et al.*, 2006). These resources help exporters understand demand trends, price dynamics, and regulatory requirements. Market intelligence enables EPAs to identify specific opportunities in foreign markets. For example, Supriyati (2023) notes that global demand for coffee continues to increase, making research essential to determine which markets have the highest potential. The ability of EPAs to generate accurate and targeted market insights is critical for exporters, especially in highly competitive commodity sectors such as coffee.

The existing literature indicates that EPAs play an important role in promoting exports, but their effectiveness varies depending on the strategies implemented. Several researchers (e.g., Cruz, 2014; Sunaryo, 2019; Hapsari & Haqqi, 2015) emphasise the importance of tailored promotion strategies, local market engagement, and strong institutional collaboration. However, few studies have exclusively analysed ITPC export promotion strategies for Indonesian coffee in the US market, particularly in the 2021–2022 period. Although previous research highlights the functional role of ITPC, it does not specifically contextualise ITPC activities using Lederman's comprehensive EPA model in the post-pandemic economic context. Therefore, this study builds on the work of Lederman *et al.* (2006) by applying the four components of the EPA as an analytical lens to analyse ITPC's coffee promotion activities in the United States. As shown in Figure 1, these four components form a conceptual framework that guides this analysis.

A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR EXPORT PROMOTION AGENCIES

Figure 1. A "Conceptual Framework of Export Promotion Agencies" (Source: Authors' Construction)

The first EPA was established in Finland in 1919. It then began to gain popularity and develop in the 1960s. Lederman *et al.* (2006) explains that the purpose of establishing an export promotion agency (EPA) is to help exporters find their markets and provide a good understanding of the products demanded in the global market. Lederman *et al.* (2006) divides this into four major categories: 1) Country Image Building 2) Export Support Services 3) Marketing 4) Research and Publications. The first is country image building, which involves efforts such as advertising, hosting promotional events, and engaging in advocacy. A country will make efforts to increase its value and develop its image to other countries in order to convince trading partners. According to Welch *et al.* (1998) most export promotion involves building networks. For example, creating and managing new connections, particularly in global markets.

The second component is export support services, where agencies offer a range of assistance to exporters. Export Support Service is defined as a service that aims to assist exporters in obtaining technical assistance, capacity building, including compliance with regulations, information on trade financing, logistics, customs, packaging, and pricing (Lederman *et al.*, 2006). The EPA, as an export promotion agency, is tasked with providing services to exporters to promote their products overseas and to gain global market share.

The third component is marketing, it can be carried out in several ways, such as export promotion agencies participating in trade fairs, missions carried out by exporters and importers, and follow-up services offered by overseas representatives (Lederman *et al.*, 2006).. Marketing is very important to expand market networks, increase the visibility of Indonesian products, and facilitate business relationships with export destination countries. In conducting marketing, export representative agencies are tasked with following up on the trade process and providing the best services to small and large businesses that have certain commodities and a strong determination to export.

The fourth category is research and publications, in which export promotion agencies or EPAs conduct market research and publications. According to Lederman *et al.* (2006) there are components of Market Research and Publications regarding general information, sectors, and company levels, such as market surveys, online information about exports, publications that encourage companies to export, and databases of exporter and importer contacts. They offer resources such as market surveys, online research tools, export publications, and databases

that connect exporters with potential importers. This information not only helps businesses make informed decisions but also encourages them to enter international markets with confidence.

Lederman *et al.* (2006) emphasize that these four categories are fundamental to the success of an EPA. Their model provides a clear framework that countries can adopt to maximize the potential of their export commodities (Cruz, 2014). This view, supported by Cruz (2014), explains that EPAs do more than just promote products; they also empower exporters to access wider international markets. By filling information gaps and providing targeted support, EPAs help domestic companies realize the full benefits of global trade. This research adopts the Export Promotion Agency concept introduced by Lederman *et al.* (2006) as a basis for analyzing how export agencies operate. The study applies this framework to better understand how institutions like ITPC promote Indonesian coffee beans in the United States.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative descriptive research design to analyse how the Indonesia Trade Promotion Centre (ITPC) promoted Indonesian coffee bean exports to the United States during the period 2021–2022. According to Sukmadinata (2011), qualitative research is used to understand social phenomena holistically by prioritising depth over quantification. A descriptive approach is appropriate for this study because it allows researchers to describe, interpret, and analyse ITPC's promotional activities in a real-world context (Priyono, 2016). Key information was obtained through official documents, press releases, and publicly available statements from the Ministry of Trade and ITPC Los Angeles and ITPC Chicago.

To ensure the credibility and reliability of the findings, this study applied several validation techniques commonly used in qualitative research. Information from ITPC documents, Ministry of Trade reports, academic literature, and expert testimony was cross-checked to ensure consistency. Official documents (e.g., Ministry of Trade press releases, ITPC reports, and statistical data) were verified to ensure authenticity and avoid reliance on unofficial sources. Cross-checking with previous studies. Findings are compared with existing research such as Sunaryo (2019), Cruz (2014) and Hapsari and Haqqi (2015) to ensure accuracy and strengthen analytical interpretation.

Primary information was obtained through official documents, press releases, and publicly available statements from the Ministry of Trade and ITPC Los Angeles and ITPC Chicago. In addition, direct insights were obtained during the Global Ready Youth National Seminar held on 29 November 2024 at the East Java National Development University 'Veteran'. During the event, researchers obtained expert information from E. Lucky Kristian, SE., MM., Head of Foreign Trade Development at the East Java Provincial Industry and Trade Office. His explanation of the role of ITPC as a market intelligence unit was an important reference for the analysis. Secondary sources include academic books, journal articles, previous studies related to EPAs and ITPC, statistical reports (e.g., BPS, 2023), and relevant online publications from official websites.

RESULTS

ITPC AS A TRADE PROMOTION AGENCIES

Export Promotion Agencies (EPAs) first began in Finland in 1919 and gained popularity and growth in the 1960s. According to Lederman *et al.* (2006), the main goal of establishing EPAs is to help exporters find their markets and understand what products are in demand globally. Lederman *et al.* (2006) divide the roles of EPAs into four main categories: Country Image Building, Export Support Services, Marketing, and Market Research and Publications. ITPC (Indonesian Trade Promotion Center) operates as one of these agencies and now runs 21 offices across various countries. Based on the EPA concept, ITPC plays a major role in promoting Indonesia's exports around the world. It focuses on identifying promising markets for Indonesian exporters and helps businesses in the U.S. find trustworthy trade partners from Indonesia. In addition to market research, ITPC Los Angeles actively develops trade-related projects that contribute to Indonesia's export growth in the U.S. There are currently two official ITPC offices operating in the United States ITPC Chicago and ITPC Los Angeles. Both offices continue to actively promote Indonesian products in the U.S. market.

COUNTRY IMAGE BUILDING

ITPC is involved in several strategic initiatives to strengthen Indonesia's image as a competitive and high-quality coffee producer. One of the main activities is Indonesia's participation in the Specialty Coffee Expo (SCE) 2021 in New Orleans, one of the largest coffee exhibitions in the world. Through the Indonesian Pavilion, ITPC showcased specialty coffees from regions such as West Java, Central Java, Aceh, Bali, Medan, and Flores. This exhibition strengthened Indonesia's branding by placing its coffee alongside leading global producers and introducing high-quality coffee beans to American buyers.

In addition, ITPC Chicago launched the Indonesia Coffee Diaspora programme in July 2021, which brought together roasters, cafes, distributors, and coffee-related businesses in the US. The programme features cupping sessions that allow stakeholders to evaluate Indonesian coffee based on Speciality Coffee Association (SCA) standards. This initiative successfully introduced Indonesian coffee varieties to American coffee professionals who previously had limited exposure to Indonesian coffee origins. Through direct engagement, ITPC strengthens Indonesia's credibility and image in the US speciality coffee market.

ITPC Chicago took the initiative to strengthen the presence of Indonesian coffee in the U.S. by opening dialogue with key coffee stakeholders in Chicago (Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia, 2021). Through this direct engagement, ITPC aimed to foster two-way communication between exporters and importers, creating a more collaborative and responsive trade environment. The Head of ITPC Chicago, Iska Huberta Simurat, shared in an official statement *"By creating space for dialogue between Indonesian producers/exporters and potential U.S. buyers, we're building stronger relationships and more people will start recognizing the quality of Indonesian coffee. We hope this strategy helps boost Indonesia's coffee export performance in the U.S."* (Ministry of Trade 2021).

Figure 2.A "Indonesia Coffee Diaspora"
Source : ITPC, 2021

EXPORT SUPPORT SERVICE

ITPC provides extensive assistance to Indonesian exporters and MSMEs to facilitate market access to the United States. These services include, technical and regulatory assistance, particularly related to certification, export standards, pricing strategies, and logistics requirements. Handling business enquiries, connecting US buyers with verified Indonesian exporters. Information dissemination through ITPC's official website and social media accounts (@itpclosangeles and @itpcchicago), which regularly publish updates on US coffee market opportunities and export-related events. A notable initiative is the collaboration between ITPC Los Angeles, ITPC Chicago, and Indonesian state-owned banks (BRI and BNI). This partnership aims to support exporters through trade financing solutions, export credit services, and mentoring programmes. These services enable MSMEs to overcome financial barriers and better prepare themselves to enter the US market (Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia, 2020). Findings show that export support services play a crucial role in reducing technical challenges and improving exporters' readiness to participate in the global coffee supply chain.

Figure 2.B "ITPC LA and ITPC Chicago Build Partnerships with Banks". (Source: Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia)

As part of its efforts to promote coffee bean exports especially to the United States the Ministry of Trade, through Indonesian Trade Promotion Centers (ITPC) in Los Angeles and Chicago, formed a partnership with two major Indonesian banks: PT BRI (Persero) and PT BNI (Persero) (Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia, 2020). This collaboration aims to support Indonesian entrepreneurs doing business in the U.S., as well as U.S. entrepreneurs looking to invest in Indonesia. They formalized this partnership by signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). Billy Anugrah, Head of ITPC Chicago, and Aidil Azhar, General Manager of BNI New York, signed the MoU at BNI's New York branch office. Under this partnership, ITPC LA and ITPC Chicago will offer trade-related banking services such as export financing and payment solutions to Indonesian MSMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises) looking to enter the U.S. market (PressRelease.id, 2020). The banks also committed to supporting export-promotion initiatives by providing training and mentoring for Indonesian entrepreneurs, especially those already active in e-commerce (Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia, 2020). In addition, they offer important market and financial information to help potential exporters prepare for international trade.

MARKETING

“Figure 3.B “Participating Trade Expo Indonesia 2022”. (Source: Metro TV)

Marketing has emerged as one of the most important aspects of ITPC's promotional activities. Several key initiatives were identified during the 2021–2022 period. ITPC actively participated in the Trade Expo Indonesia (TEI), an international B2B business exhibition showcasing Indonesian commodities ready for export. The agency selected quality coffee exhibitors, facilitated business matchmaking sessions, and provided promotional support through digital and print media. TEI enables Indonesian coffee suppliers to interact directly with US buyers, potentially resulting in trade agreements and broader market access.

“Figure 3.D Hybrid Coffee Business Matching”. (Source: Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia)

In April 2021, ITPC Los Angeles collaborated with the Indonesian Consulate General to hold a hybrid business matching and coffee cupping session (Ministry of Trade and Industry of Indonesia, 2021). Indonesian MSMEs participated virtually, while US-based café owners and coffee processors attended in person. The tasting session allowed buyers to evaluate the quality of the coffee beans, while the business matching session facilitated direct communication regarding pricing, logistics, and supply capacity (Indonesia Coffee Diaspora, 2021).

Promotional Materials And Thematic Branding

During the Indonesia Coffee Diaspora programme, ITPC Chicago developed promotional brochures containing detailed agro-climatic profiles, origin characteristics, and flavour notes of Indonesian coffee. These materials used the thematic concept 'From Origin to Global Market; From Farmer to Cup', designed to highlight Indonesia's coffee heritage and strengthen its marketing narrative. This strategy helped US stakeholders better understand the identity of Indonesian coffee, especially those who had never visited Indonesia. Overall, ITPC's marketing activities successfully strengthened visibility, buyer engagement, and product positioning in the US market.

RESEARCH AND PUBLICATIONS

As an export agency, ITPC consistently conducts market research and publishes valuable resources. Their research includes general market information, online export-related insights, publications that encourage companies to export, and databases of exporter and importer contacts. The components of Market Research and Publication cover a range of areas general information, sector-specific data, and company-level insights. These include market surveys, online export information, export-promotion publications, and contact databases for both exporters and importers (Lederman *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 5.A "Shows That Coffee Consumption is Highest in the United States. (Source: Coffee Diaspora)

ITPC has conducted in-depth research on companies interested in importing coffee from Indonesia. According to the (Indonesia Coffee Diaspora, 2021), ITPC Chicago studied the U.S. market thoroughly, including the average daily coffee consumption habits of Americans. Their research revealed that over 50% of Americans aged 18 and above drink coffee every day. ITPC Chicago approached this research with precision, especially when identifying potential buyers in the U.S. These buyers don't just understand coffee they also have the capacity to place large-volume orders. ITPC didn't stop there; they also invited coffee experts and café owners to join the event, ensuring that their efforts aligned with broader national goals.

In addition, ITPC researched coffee pricing in the U.S. and explored potential pricing strategies for Indonesian coffee in the market. With around 27 participants from roasteries and coffee companies attending, ITPC viewed this as a strong strategy to introduce Indonesian coffee directly to potential U.S. buyers (ITPC, 2021). This clearly shows that ITPC has carried out effective market research for Indonesian coffee exporters. They managed to attract serious, high-potential buyers while also identifying the demographics in the U.S. that consume the most coffee and the types of coffee they prefer. ITPC's research has proven incredibly helpful for business owners looking to understand and reach their ideal market. According to Lucky Kristian, SE, MM, Head of Foreign Trade Development at the East Java Provincial Office of Industry and Trade, "ITPC serves as a market intelligence body it reports, predicts, and surprises

buyers abroad. "ITPC's presence proves that Indonesian entrepreneurs and coffee exporters have an equal opportunity to showcase their best products to the global market.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that the Indonesia Trade Promotion Centre (ITPC) played a multidimensional role in promoting Indonesian coffee bean exports to the United States during the period 2021–2022. When analysed using the Export Promotion Agency (EPA) framework introduced by Lederman *et al.* (2006), ITPC activities demonstrate alignment with the four core functions of an EPA: Country Image Building, Export Support Services, Marketing, and Market Research & Publications. This section discusses the significance of these findings and interprets them in a broader theoretical and policy context. The results of the study show that ITPC's promotional strategy strongly supports the theoretical proposition of Lederman *et al.* (2006).

The development of the country's image is achieved through participation in international exhibitions and special programmes such as Indonesia Coffee Diaspora. These efforts support the argument that national branding and visibility are very important for increasing export competitiveness. The Export Support Services provided by ITPC including technical guidance, financial facilitation, and market information reflect the EPA's role in reducing information barriers and transaction costs for exporters. Marketing activities such as business matchmaking, cupping sessions, and participation in the Trade Expo Indonesia (TEI) are in line with the idea that direct interaction with buyers increases market entry opportunities. Market Research and Publications confirm Lederman *et al.* (2006) assertion that the EPA functions as a knowledge institution, providing data that enables exporters to make informed decisions. Therefore, the Indonesian case reinforces the EPA model and demonstrates how comprehensive implementation of the four components can support export growth in specific commodity sectors.

ITPC activities appear to have made a positive contribution to strengthening Indonesia's position in the US specialty coffee market. Events such as SCE 2021 and hybrid business matchmaking sessions enable Indonesian suppliers to interact directly with US roasters and cafes segments that have high demand for specialty coffee and high-scoring coffee. By facilitating direct product evaluation through cupping sessions, ITPC reduces the perceived risk for potential buyers, which is particularly important for agricultural commodities that depend on sensory attributes. Financial facilitation through partnerships with BRI and BNI also increases the readiness of MSMEs to enter the US market. According to the literature, providing access to trade finance can significantly increase the likelihood of successful export transactions (Cruz, 2014). This shows that ITPC's approach combines promotional activities with structural support, thereby strengthening its overall impact.

Despite these achievements, the findings also highlight several challenges faced by ITPC and Indonesian exporters. A lack of awareness among MSMEs regarding ITPC services, resulting in suboptimal utilisation of available promotional facilities. Limited understanding of export requirements, including SCA standards, quality consistency, certification, and logistics procedures. Financial barriers faced by small producers seeking to participate in international exhibitions or obtain export financing. The need to establish long-term relationships, which is particularly important in the US coffee market where buyers prefer consistent supply, transparent traceability, and stable quality. These challenges reflect structural issues often faced by emerging economies in export promotion and emphasise the need for stronger domestic capacity-building initiatives.

To address these challenges, several policy-based solutions can be considered. Enhanced extension programmes by ITPC to inform MSMEs and cooperatives about available export support services. Capacity building initiatives such as workshops on cupping standards, export documentation and digital marketing. Subsidised participation schemes to help small coffee producers attend international trade fairs. Improved supply chain traceability, enabling Indonesian coffee to compete more effectively with established producers such as Brazil, Colombia and Vietnam. These policy measures will complement ITPC's promotional strategy and enhance the long-term sustainability of Indonesia's coffee export performance.

When compared to similar institutions in Southeast Asia such as MATRADE Malaysia or Enterprise Singapore ITPC's activities show striking similarities, particularly in terms of exhibition participation and buyer engagement. However, MATRADE places greater emphasis on exporter training and export readiness programmes, while Enterprise Singapore integrates digital export platforms and innovation-based promotion. This comparison suggests that Indonesia could get the benefit from expanding its focus beyond promotional events to include structured exporter enhancement programmes, particularly for coffee producers in rural areas.

CONCLUSION

Coffee beans remain one of Indonesia's most strategic export commodities, especially in the United States market where demand for specialty and high-quality coffee continues to increase. This study analyzes how the Indonesia Trade Promotion Center (ITPC) in Los Angeles and Chicago promoted Indonesian coffee bean exports during the 2021–2022 period by applying the Export Promotion Agency (EPA) framework developed by Lederman *et al.* (2006). The results of the study show that the ITPC carried out various promotional, facilitation, and market intelligence activities that collectively supported Indonesia's export performance during the post-pandemic recovery period. This analysis confirms that the four main components of the EPA model Country Image Building, Export Support Services, Marketing, and Market Research & Publications were implemented in an integrated and consistent manner. Through major international exhibitions such as the 2021 Specialty Coffee Expo (SCE) and the Indonesia Coffee Diaspora program, ITPC strengthened Indonesia's branding as a producer of high-quality, diverse, and competitive coffee. These events provided opportunities for Indonesian suppliers to interact directly with coffee roasters, distributors, and cafes in the US, which is crucial for a commodity that is highly dependent on sensory quality and buyer confidence.

In addition, this study highlights the crucial role of export support services in facilitating the participation of MSMEs and coffee cooperatives in the global supply chain. ITPC assistance in the form of regulatory guidance, logistical information, and buyer verification helps reduce barriers that often hinder new exporters. The collaboration between ITPC and Indonesian state-owned banks (BRI and BNI) further enhances exporters' readiness by providing access to financing solutions, training, and technical resources. This demonstrates that export promotion requires not only visibility and marketing, but also structural support mechanisms that help domestic businesses overcome systemic constraints. Marketing activities, particularly TEI 2021–2022 and hybrid business matching sessions, illustrate a shift towards more adaptive and flexible promotion formats. This hybrid strategy allows for broader participation, especially for SME exporters with limited financial capacity to physically attend overseas events. These activities also facilitate direct communication with buyers, strengthen trust-building efforts, and increase the likelihood of securing long-term trade partnerships.

Market research and publications compiled by ITPC have proven to be equally important. By analysing US consumer behaviour, price trends, and importer profiles, ITPC equips Indonesian

exporters with valuable insights that can guide production decisions, quality improvements, and market entry strategies. These results reinforce the argument that EPAs should not only function as promotional bodies, but also as reliable sources of market information that help exporters anticipate and respond to global market dynamics.

However, the study also identifies several areas for improvement. Many MSMEs are still unaware of ITPC services, and there are still gaps in exporters' understanding of the necessary certifications, SCA standards, and quality consistency required by US buyers. These challenges highlight the need for stronger domestic coordination, expanded training programmes, and greater awareness-raising efforts. Enhancing the capacity of exporters at the domestic level is essential to ensure that overseas promotional activities can generate sustainable export results.

These findings indicate that ITPC plays a significant and multifaceted role in Indonesia's export ecosystem. ITPC's strategy during the 2021–2022 period not only supported an increase in coffee export volume but also strengthened Indonesia's reputation in the speciality coffee segment. This study contributes to the literature by applying the EPA framework to a specific commodity context and by describing how the EPA has adapted its role in the post-pandemic era through hybrid events, integrated financial facilitation, and targeted market intelligence. For policymakers, this research emphasises the importance of maintaining strong synergies between promotion agencies, financial institutions, exporters, and local governments to strengthen Indonesia's global position in the coffee industry.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest in publishing this paper.

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